

CONTEXTUALIZED ARTWORK INSTRUCTIONAL VIDEO: BASIS FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN ARTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559430>

ABSTRACT

This study, “Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video: Basis for Improving Students' Performance in Arts,” aimed to identify the effects of contextualized artwork instructional videos on the performance skills of grade 8 students in arts. The quasi-experimental method was employed. The participants of the study were the grade 8 sections A and B with 32 equal numbers of students for a total of 64 students. The instruments used were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, the Paired T-test, and the T-test for independent mean. The following were the findings of the said study: before the use of the self-learning module and contextualized artwork instructional video, both groups had a low level of performance when taken as a whole. Furthermore, after utilizing the self-learning modules and contextualized artwork instructional video when taken as a whole, the Control Group remains at a very low level of performance while the experimental group improves to a very high level of performance. Moreover, results showed that the level of student performance with the use of the self-learning modules and contextualized artwork instructional video was highly significant because the Control Group's level of performance remained at a low level while the Experimental group improved their level of performance after utilizing contextualized artwork instructional video in teaching Arts. The researcher concluded that the contextualized artwork instructional video was effective in improving students' level of performance in Arts. Thus, the teacher must accompany the self-learning modules with contextualized

artwork instructional videos so that the students may be able to appreciate the applications of concepts and skills in doing their artwork.

Keywords: *Modular, arts, modular, video-based, instructional material*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching as defined is the process of imparting knowledge and skills to the students. Moreover, effective teaching is based on the result of the assessment where the learners successfully manifest the mastery of the lessons' objectives (Baldwin, 2021). MAPEH, as one of the subjects in junior high school which stands for Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health, is considered a practical and 'hands-on' subject, where proximity and application of lessons learned are common (Dinglasan & Villa, 2019). However, the coronavirus pandemic has had a significant impact on more than 190 countries, with over 1.5 billion students affected in schools that have had to resort to nationwide closures (Soliven, 2020).

Most nations have temporarily shut down educational institutions to stop the spread of the virus and lower infections as a result of the widespread disruption brought on by COVID-19, including travel restrictions, the global economic downturn, and the closure of schools (Tria, 2020). As the country continues to confront different issues brought about by the pandemic, the Department of Education is addressing the challenges in basic education for the school year 2020-2021 through its Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan under DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020 (DepEd, 2020). Thus, paving the way for the implementation of distance learning in all schools in the Philippines.

Per DepEd Order No. 012's s.2020, DepEd hereby adopts distance learning. Distance learning is a method of delivering education in which the teacher and students are physically separated from one another while receiving instruction. According to data obtained through DepEd's National Learner Enrolment and Survey Forms (LESFs), 8.8 million of the 22.2 million enrollees (or 39.6% of all respondents) preferred modular distance learning for the upcoming academic year. In modular distance learning, students receive individualized instruction and are given the option to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital form (electronic copy), depending on the learner's situation, as well as other learning resources like textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other study materials (Manlangit et al., 2020).

Utilizing modules promotes independent study. The concepts covered in the module are learned by the students at their own pace and exploration (Natividad, 2021). However, at some point, due to incomplete instructions in the module and the fact that some students barely understood the instructions, students' output in the performance task is affected, which leads to low scores in the performance task, but instructional videos can be a big help (Alber, 2019).

An instructional video is any video used to educate a particular lesson. It might be a DVD with instructions, or it might be videos that can be downloaded online and viewed on an MP3 player or computer screen from websites like YouTube (Christensen, 2022). Videos are an excellent medium for communicating ideas because they are interesting to watch, can hold a lot of information, are simple to create, and are simple to share. Thus, instructional videos should be used in other subjects as well (Borromeo, et al., 2020).

It is in this context that the researcher conducted this study to improve the level of performance of the students in creating contextualized artworks in Arts using an Instructional Video. Thus, this study aims to determine the effects of contextualized artwork instructional video on the performance skills of grade 8 students in Arts.

Review of Related Literature

Teaching Art

In the midst of the pandemic, we are discussing the viability of distance education. As educators and parents, we are concerned about how the widespread closing of schools may affect our students' ability to learn. As school systems work to make up for lost learning, there is also concern that they will start to prioritize certain subjects over others. And frequently, when making these kinds of choices, the arts are sacrificed. However, I contend that the arts are the most important right now. Crisis inspires creativity, and these inspirations don't always revolve around amusing ways to pass the time. The key to innovation is creativity. And that might be the key that saves us all (Wolpert-Gawron, 2020).

For much of the twentieth century, the central idea in art education has been that art is more than just creative expression (Davis & Walling, 2021). For our young people to express themselves freely, communicate, explore, use their imagination, and comprehend culture and history, the arts are crucial. They have long been recognized as an integral part of the human affective experience. Moreover, the value of arts education is demonstrated by the ability of schools to teach students about ethics, help them understand social realities, and help them understand their rights and obligations as well (Punzalan, 2018). Teaching art isn't easy but even harder. If you entered this situation believing it to be simple and you don't enjoy a challenge, you might be in the wrong line of work. There aren't many greater goals in life, but if you take on the challenge and put your all into it, you can inspire a generation of students to express themselves creatively and transform lives. Students who are taught effectively often produce works of art of high quality. It makes no difference where you teach. No matter what your budget is. It doesn't matter what the socioeconomic and demographic status of your school is. You will have talented art students if you are an effective teacher (Fussell, 2019).

Galvez (2018) asserted that each student reacts to information in various ways. In order to effectively teach a lesson's subject matter, it is frequently advantageous for teachers to employ a variety of approaches and strategies. Punzalan (2018) also asserted that

children do learn well through play and experimentation. These techniques can be used to encourage this learning across all curriculum areas. Students' participation and confidence are increased when visual arts are used in various learning areas. Their knowledge and skills also advance as they enjoy creating art. Individualization of learning may be beneficial for each student. For example, learning mathematical concepts through art (space, perspective, angles, shapes, etc.), learning social and environmental concepts through art and crafts (dress, lifestyles, housing, etc.), learning scientific concepts through art (light, colors, and color mixing, etc.), and some assessment through technique rather than other methods like tests may all be effective. You can improve almost any subject (Punzalan, 2018).

Modular Distance Learning

Modular learning is a type of distance learning that makes use of Self-Learning Modules (SLM) based on the most important learning competencies (MELCS) provided by DepEd. The modules contain sections on assessment and motivation that provide a comprehensive roadmap for teachers' and students' desired competencies. Through home visits that adhere to social distancing protocols and feedback mechanisms, teachers will keep track of their students' progress and help those who require it (Manlangit et al, 2020).

Based on data gathered via DepEd's National Learner Enrolment and Survey Forms (LESFs), 8.8 million out of the 22.2 million enrollees (39.6% of total respondents) preferred modular distance learning for the upcoming school year. In contrast, 3.9 million students (17.6%) preferred blended learning, 3.8 million (17.1%) preferred online learning, and 1.4 million and 900,000 students, respectively, preferred learning through television and radio (Manlangit et al, 2020).

In order to accommodate different types of learners throughout the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) will provide Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with alternative learning delivery modalities. The integration of SLMs with alternative learning delivery modalities (modular, television- and radio-based instruction, blended learning, and online) will assist DepEd in ensuring that all students have access to high-quality basic education for SY 2020–2021, despite the fact that face-to-face instruction is still not permitted due to the current state of the public health. Schools that are located in coastal areas, far-flung provinces, and communities without access to the internet or electricity delivered SLMs in printed format. The Department has announced that SLMs can also be accessed online or offline for homes with gadgets and devices. The Department also affirmed that because SLMs can be completed at home, the well-being of the staff and teachers will come first. Teachers must adhere to the current work arrangement and health protocols if they need to travel to their schools to obtain materials for the SLMs (DepEd, 2020).

Sareen (2019) conducted a study to compare the relative efficacy of self-learning modules and traditional teaching methods on class IX students' acquisition of process skills concerning their study habits. With a pre-test and post-test non-equivalent group

design, the current investigation was experimental and used a quasi-experimental methodology. A sample of 200 students, 100 in the control group and 100 in the experimental group participated in the study. Self-learning modules were used to teach the experimental group, while traditional classroom instruction was used to teach the same material to the control group. N.S. used an achievement test in process skills that were created by the researcher as a pretest, post-test, and study habits inventory. For data collection, Yadav was utilized. T-test and 2X2 ANOVA were used to analyze the collected data. The study's findings showed that both traditional and self-learning modules, or teaching methods, help students improve their process skills. However, teaching through self-learning modules is more successful than traditional methods of teaching because it yields a significantly higher gain in process skills than traditional methods of teaching.

According to the study by Dargo and Dimas (2021), the academic performance of learners after the implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) decreased. They proposed that the administration focus on enhancing and streamlining worksheets or workbooks that will be given out to students, along with videos of lessons that are in line with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) (Dargo & Dimas, 2021). The great number of activities in each module and not enough time to answer all the modules within a week are the main problems that emerged in the implementation of Modular Distance Learning (Sumaoang & Dangle, 2020).

Ambayon (2020) asserted that when compared to traditional teaching methods, modular instruction was more effective because it allowed students to learn at their own pace. The student-centered approach to learning is strengthened by this type of learning modality. For teachers, students, and parents, the introduction of modular instruction did, however, present several difficulties. The study by Sumaoang and Dangle (2020) revealed that the main issues were: a lack of school funding for the creation and delivery of modules; students' difficulties with independent learning; and parents' lack of expertise in academic child-rearing.

Moreover, Natividad (2021) asserted in his study that SLMs were not effective in the implementation of MDL. According to the study's findings, the SLM's perceived efficacy in implementing MDL at this scale and magnitude during this pandemic will likely depend on the usability and content quality of the tool. The SLM's usability, content quality, or teachers' implemented interventions did not appear to have any causal impact on learners' perceptions of the SLM's perceived effectiveness. The outcome suggests that students might not fully comprehend the context of their learning to assess it using the SLM.

Instructional Video

Any video that can fit on an MP3 player, computer screen, or website like YouTube is what we call an instructional video. They can also be found on instructional DVDs or downloaded online (Christensen, 2022). Videos are an excellent medium for

communicating ideas because they are interesting to watch, can hold a lot of information, are simple to create, and are simple to share. Thus, instructional videos should be used in other subjects as well (Borromeo, et al., 2020).

Brown (2021) believes that using videos in the classroom is a great idea. This is a fun experiment for kids as well, and they will undoubtedly enjoy the entire experience to start. It offers a teacher a wide range of extraordinary benefits. When used in a classroom setting or learning session, videos have a lot of advantages. According to Brown (2021), the following are some of the main advantages of using videos in the classroom: Students are more open to watching videos; it immerses students in the production; it stimulates activities; videos bring more information and engage learners; they integrate the outside world into the classroom; videos can tell more than words; videos are more flexible and easier to understand; and above all, videos create an experience.

Almuslamani et al., (2020) discussed in their study that the use of educational videos has a direct and positive effect on student participation in the classroom. When the students have the option to choose the videos themselves, this effect is amplified. It was evident that the teachers actively encouraged their students to participate in class by encouraging them to ask questions, express their opinions, and engage in related discussions. Additionally, these videos inspired the students to actively participate in class by taking notes, remaining quiet, and paying attention to the lecturer.

Wijnker et al. (2018) found that watching videos with questions increased students' interest and watching videos with knowledgeable speakers increased their self-reported conceptual knowledge gains. Additionally, teachers frequently chose and incorporated videos into their lessons based solely on intuition rather than having clear objectives for doing so. The use of videos might be improved by encouraging teachers to use them in a more purposeful manner.

According to Calado (2021) in her study "The Effectiveness of Instructional Video in Teaching Grade 10 Araling Panlipunan", the study concluded that using instructional videos effectively engages students with the material, deepens understanding, and increases retention. It can produce experiences that are not limited to print media. Moreover, they offer an accessible resource that can be accessed from anywhere. There are numerous ways to use videos in a learning environment.

Importance of Instructional Video in Teaching Art

Teachers always strive to show more and tell less when introducing the students to new information, concepts, and skills. An instructional video can be a great tool to assist students in gaining a deeper understanding of content. It's crucial to be conscientious of how frequently and extensively we use instructional videos, and it's significant to have a specific goal before using a movie, documentary, or news clip (Alber, 2019). The utilization in the classroom of instructional videos is not new. Students' cooperation and creativity are increased by video-based learning materials. Video is the most accessible medium for both teachers and students because every classroom in the school has a

built-in TV monitor, which can help motivate students and give their learning experience a unique context (Calado, 2021).

Barbaro (2021) claimed that Michael Noetel and colleagues formalized a meta-analysis of 105 published research studies. To provide a comprehensive assessment of an intervention's effectiveness—in this case, the use of instructional videos in comparison to more conventional learning methods like in-person lectures. The findings lend credence to the notion that students can benefit most from independently viewing recorded instructional material outside of class. The authors contend that videos are frequently more streamlined and edited than live lectures, along with the ability for students to progress through the information at their own pace (rewind, re-watch, etc.), which will help students retain the information.

According to Lalian (2018), who conducted a study titled "The Effects of Using Video Media in Learning on Students' Cognitive and Affective Aspects," the use of learning videos places a greater emphasis on cognitive than on affective aspects to accomplish learning goals. However, despite the fact that using videos places a greater emphasis on cognitive aspects, it can also boost students' motivation and interest in their studies. Additionally, it is thought that students who are highly motivated or interested in what they are learning will find it easier to meet their goals. Instructional videos can be used to transmit conceptual knowledge provided the information presentation follows the steps or procedure of the activity (Muhidin & Wibawa, 2021).

Research Questions

The objective of the study was to identify the effects of contextualized artwork instructional video on the performance skills of grade 8 students in Arts. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of student's performance before the use of contextualized artwork instructional video and self-learning module when taken as a whole and in terms of:
 - a. Following directions
 - b. Creativity and workmanship
 - c. Pattern
2. What is the level of student performance after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video and self-learning modules when taken as a whole and in terms of:
 - a. Following directions
 - b. Creativity and workmanship
 - c. Pattern
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of the students' performance before and after the use of self-learning module?

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of the students' performance before and after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video?
5. Is there a significant difference between the use of self-learning modules and contextualized artwork instructional video in the level of students' performance?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed the Quasi-Experimental research design. According to Thomas (2020), a quasi-experimental design aimed to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable. A quasi-experiment does not rely on random assignment. Instead, subjects were assigned to groups based on non-random criteria. It includes pretest and posttest, and there is a control group and a test group. A purposive sampling technique was used in determining the participants of the study. Two sections of grade 8 were utilized as the participants of the study. The participants were chosen from sections A and B with an equal number of 32 students from Section A and 32 students from Section B. Section A was the control group while section B was the experimental group. The researcher used the standardized rubric using the Likert Scale with the following criteria: following directions, creativity and workmanship, and pattern. Each criterion followed the scaling system with 4 points as the highest score that corresponds to excellent, 3 as good, 2 as fair, and 1 point as the lowest score corresponding to poor. The standardized rubric was validated using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio by C.H. Lawshe, with 10 jurors that were selected and requested to conduct a face and content validation of the research instrument. Upon consolidation of the ratings given by the validators, the Content validity index of the rubric was 0.82. Also, the rubric established 0.782 which results in good inter-rater reliability results. The study was composed of a pretest and a posttest. The pretest was given to both sections of Grade 8 through a self-learning module. They followed the instructions on the self-learning module on how to make their performance task in Art. Then, the parents were the ones to submit the performance task to their MAPEH teacher. Students' output is rated individually using a standardized rubric. The researcher collected the data and checked the output of the students. For the posttest, Grade 8-Section A utilized again the self-learning module while Grade 8-Section B utilized the contextualized artwork instructional video made by the MAPEH teacher. Students' output is rated individually using a standardized rubric. The researcher collected the data and checked the output of the students. Specifically, the objective of the study was guided by the following data and analyses procedure: To determine the level of students' performance with the use of contextualized artwork instructional video and self-learning module, the mean and the standard deviation were utilized in the study. To determine if there is a significant difference in the level of the students' performance before and after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video and self-learning module, the Paired T-test was utilized. To determine if there is a significant difference between the use of self-learning modules and contextualized artwork

instructional video in the level of students' performance, the t-test for Independent Means was utilized in the study.

RESULTS

Table 1

Level of Students' Performance Before the use of Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video and Self-Learning Module

Criterion	CONTROL GROUP			EXPERIMENTAL GROUP		
	Mean	SD	V I	Mean	SD	V I
Following directions	1.563	.801	Very Low	1.750	.803	Very Low
Creativity and workmanship	1.688	.780	Very Low	1.781	.870	Low
Pattern	2.281	.924	Low	2.375	.942	Low
As a whole	1.828	.297	Low	1.957	.330	Low

Note. The mean scores are interpreted as follows: 1.00 – 1.75 (Very Low), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low), 2.51 – 3.25 (High), 3.26 – 4.00 (Very high).

Table 2

Level of Students' Performance After the Use of Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video and Self-Learning Module

Criterion	CONTROL GROUP			EXPERIMENTAL GROUP		
	Mean	SD	V I	Mean	SD	V I
Following directions	1.719	.813	Very Low	3.406	.798	Very High
Creativity and workmanship	1.688	.738	Very Low	3.000	1.200	High
Pattern	1.813	.860	Low	3.438	1.045	Very High
As a whole	1.742	.420	Very Low	3.312	.694	Very High

Note. The mean scores are interpreted as follows: 1.00 – 1.75 (Very Low), 1.76 – 2.50 (Low), 2.51 – 3.25 (High), 3.26 – 4.00 (Very high).

Table 3

Significant Difference in the Level of Students' Performance Before and After the Use of Self-Learning Module

	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	df	p	Interpretation	Decision
Before	32	1.828	.297	0.087	.571	31	.572	Not Significant	Accept
After	32	1.742	.420						

Note. **The mean difference is significant, $p < .001$

Table 4

Significant Difference in the Level of Students' Performance Before and After the Use of Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video

	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	df	p	Interpretation	Decision
Before	32	1.957	.330	- 1.355	- 9.294	31	.000	Highly	Reject
After	32	3.312	.694					Significant	

Note. **The mean difference is significant, $p < .001$

Table 5

Significant Difference in the Level of Students' Performance Between the Use of Self-Learning Module and Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video

	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	df	p	Interpretation	Decision
SLM	32	1.742	.420	- 1.57	- 9.819	62	.000	Highly	Reject
CAIV	32	3.312	.694					Significant	

Note. **The mean difference is significant, $p < .001$

DISCUSSION

Level of Students' Performance Before the use of Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video and Self-Learning Module

Table 1 shows that the Control Group level of students' performance according to the set criteria ranges from very low to low with Pattern having the highest mean of 2.281 and standard deviation, of .924 and Creativity and Workmanship having the lowest mean of 1.563 and standard deviation of .801. The performance results of the

Experimental Group also range from very low to low level of students' performances. Again, the pattern has the highest mean of 2.375 and a standard deviation of .942, and the following directions have the lowest mean of 1.750 and a standard deviation of .803. When taken as a whole, both the Control Group and the Experimental Group has Low level of students' performance with a mean of 1.828 and 1.957 and a standard deviation of .297 and .330 accordingly.

This indicates that modular distance learning is somewhat ineffective because students are taking the modules for granted. Due to the fact that the modules require extensive reading and are meant to stimulate independent learning, students didn't take them seriously. Sometimes, students don't understand much of what is in the module. At some point, students struggle with self-study due to a lack of interest in reading and incomplete instructions in the module. Likewise, parents can't guide them due to a lack of knowledge of academics. That is why students' performance is affected. It is clear that using modular distance learning causes students to struggle.

Ambayon (2020) asserted that when compared to traditional teaching methods, modular instruction was more effective because it allowed students to learn at their own pace. The student-centered approach to learning is strengthened by this type of learning modality. For teachers, students, and parents, the introduction of modular instruction did, however, present several difficulties. The study by Sumaoang and Dangle (2020) revealed that the main issues were: a lack of school funding for the creation and delivery of modules; students' difficulties with independent learning; and parents' lack of expertise in academic child-rearing. This implies that the module should be read and taken seriously by the students. Likewise, the teacher should try to consider other teaching strategies to support the students' learning, such as creating an instructional video.

Level of Students' Performance After the Use of Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video and Self-Learning Module

Table 2 presents the level of students' performance after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video and self-learning module. Accordingly, Control Group when under the self-learning module, each criterion for performance level ranges from very low to low with a Pattern having the highest mean of 1.813 and standard deviation of .860, and Creativity and Workmanship having the lowest mean of 1.688 and standard deviation of .738. Lastly, when taken as a whole after using the self-learning module, students' performance is still very low with a mean of 1.742 and a standard deviation of .420. This implies that students' performance didn't improve after using the self-learning module.

However, Experimental Group after using contextualized artwork instructional video, as shown in the table, both the level of performances in Pattern are Very High, with a mean of 3.438 and a standard deviation of 1.045, and Following Directions with the mean of 3.406 and standard deviation of .798, given respectively. While Creativity and

Workmanship remain High with a mean of 3.000 and a standard deviation of 1.200. Lastly, when taken as a whole after using contextualized artwork instructional video students' performance is Very High with a mean of 3.312 and a standard deviation of .694.

This indicates that self-learning modules are ineffective because students find it hard to understand the instruction in the modules due to a lack of interest in reading. But when using contextualized artwork instructional, the performance of the students improved because instructional video helps students understand the instruction more by simply watching the video. Likewise, it easily attracts students because of the text and images, where students can easily follow what's in the video. Moreover, instructional videos help boost the creativity of the students by creating distinct contexts based on their own perspectives and experiences.

Instructional videos can be used to transmit conceptual knowledge provided the information presentation follows the steps or procedure of the activity (Muhidin & Wibawa, 2021). Using videos in the classroom is an excellent idea, not only does this provide a teacher with a wide range of extraordinary benefits but it's a fun experiment for students as well and they will certainly appreciate the entire experience, to begin with (Brown, 2021). This implies that contextualized instructional video was effective in the sense that the performance of the students improved a lot. Students find it helpful that is why they were motivated to do the activity because they already have a guide. Thus, the students should watch attentively the video and the teacher should create more contextualized instructional videos to support the modules and the learning of the students.

Significant Difference in the Level of Students' Performance Before and After the Use of Self-Learning Module

The table shows that there is no significant difference between Pretest scores ($M=1.828, SD=.297$) and Posttest scores ($M=1.742, SD=.420$), $t(.571)=0.087$, $p<.572$ at 5% level of significance. It displays that the level of students' performance is not significant with a mean of 1.828 and a standard deviation of .297 before the use of the self-learning module, and after the use of the self-learning module with the mean of 1.742 and a standard deviation of .420, and having a mean difference of 0.087.

This indicates that the performance of the students didn't improve when using the self-learning module. Unfortunately, it adds to the burden on the students' because the sample photo is unclear and the instructions are difficult to understand due to the smaller text font. As a result, they are unable to identify the proper pattern.

The great number of activities in each module and having not enough time to answer all the modules within a week are the main problems that emerged in the implementation of Modular Distance Learning (Sumaong & Dangle, 2020). According to the study by Dargo and Dimas (2021), the performance of learners in academics after the implementation of Modular Distance Learning (MDL) decreased. They proposed that the administration focus on enhancing and streamlining worksheets or workbooks that

will be given out to students, along with videos of lessons that are in line with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) (Dargo & Dimas, 2021). Video lessons were more effective in all learning competencies, though modular approaches in some areas were also effective for students during this difficult time. Even without the assistance of a teacher, video lessons helped students comprehend and understand the lessons better. In light of the aforementioned information and data, a learning experience that combines video lessons and modular teaching methods will be effective (Bullo, 2021). Thus, it implies that the teacher should accompany the modules with instructional videos to support and give clearer instructions on the activity to the students.

Significant Difference in the Level of Students' Performance Before and After the Use of Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video

The table below shows that there is a significant difference between Pretest scores ($M=1.957, SD=.330$) and Posttest scores ($M=3.312, SD=.694$), $t(-9.294)=-1.355$, $p<.000$ at 5% level of significance. It shows that the level of students' performance is highly significant with a mean of 1.957 and a standard deviation of .330 before the contextualized artwork instructional video and after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video with the mean of 3.312 and a standard deviation of .694, and having a mean difference of -1.355 .

Results showed there is a significant difference in the level of students' performance after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video. This implies that the use of contextualized artwork instructional videos on improving students' performance is effective in the sense that students were able to unfold, explore, and analyze the learning process on their own, which gave them greater chances of making their own creative masterpieces and mastering the skills needed.

Videos are an excellent medium for communicating ideas because they are interesting to watch, can hold a lot of information, are simple to create, and are simple to share (Borromeo, et al., 2020). Based on the study conducted by Lalian (2018), using instructional videos placed a greater emphasis on cognitive than affective factors. However, it can also boost students' enthusiasm and interest in their studies. It is anticipated that students who are highly motivated or interested in learning may find it easier to accomplish their learning goals (Lalian, 2018).

Significant Difference in the Level of Students' Performance Between the Use of Self-Learning Module and Contextualized Artwork Instructional Video

The table above shows that there is a significant difference between Pretest scores ($M=1.957, SD=.330$) and Posttest scores ($M=3.312, SD=.694$), $t(-9.294)=-1.355$, $p<.000$ at 5% level of significance. It shows that the level of students' performance is highly significant with a mean of 1.742 and a standard deviation of .420 with the use of self-learning module, and the use of contextualized artwork instructional video with the mean of 3.312 and a standard deviation of .694, and having a mean difference of -1.57 .

This indicates that contextualized artwork instructional videos are a more effective strategy for enhancing students' creativity and skill mastery than self-learning modules, which are more geared toward the needs of the students. Self-learning modules are considered student-centered in the sense that students must understand and learn modules on their own in which they are unable to determine whether their presumptions are true or false.

Getting frustrated or stressed when lessons are hard to understand and getting easily distracted while studying are the negative effects of modules on the students which is why students tend to disregard their modules (Tombaga, et al., 2021). However, through instructional videos, learners can control his/her learning process. Learners can pause, stop, rewind, and then manipulate the timeline of creating a distinct artwork (Beheshti, et al, 2018). Moreover, whenever an on-screen instructor draws images on the board while lecturing, guides the audience's gaze while lecturing, includes prompts for summarizing or explaining the material, films a demonstration in the first person, or includes subtitles, students learn more from the instructional video (Mayer et al, 2020).

This implies that students improved their performance through contextualized artwork instructional videos rather than self-learning modules. That is why teachers must accompany the modules with instructional videos for a better understanding of the students for the said activities. Likewise, students must watch the videos attentively and engage themselves to have meaningful learning.

As reflected in the results, this study was supported by the theory of learning by doing by John Dewey because students learn more through engaging themselves in the activity given by the teacher. Through direct experience, students enjoy the activity and learn as well, because the more they enjoy what they do, the deeper motivation to learn and mastery of the skills comes afterward. Also, this study was associated with the pragmatic philosophy, wherein their experiences directly relate to their day-to-day lives. That is why learning becomes concrete and meaningful. By integrating contextualized artwork instructional video, students were given a chance to experience and do the task on their own. Likewise, students can pause, stop, rewind, and then manipulate the timeline of making the artwork. That is why students have the confidence to create distinct artwork based on their own perspectives and experiences.

Conclusions

The following were the findings of the said study. Before the use of the self-learning module and contextualized artwork instructional video, both groups have a very low level of performance in following directions, creativity, and workmanship. However, in terms of pattern, the Control Group has a low level of performance, while the Experimental Group has a very low level of performance in following directions and a low level in creativity and workmanship, and pattern. Both groups have a low level of performance when taken as a whole. Furthermore, after utilizing the self-learning

modules and contextualized artwork instructional video, Control Group remains having a low level of performance in terms of pattern and a very low level of performance in following directions, and creativity and workmanship. However, the Experimental Group improved in all criteria. They have a high level of performance in creativity and workmanship and a very high level of performance in terms of following directions and Patterns. Lastly, when taken as a whole, the Control Group remains at a very low level of performance while the Experimental Group improves to a very high Level of Performance.

In terms of the significant difference in the level of student's performance before and after the use of self-learning module, results show that there is no significant in the level of student's performance before and after the use of the self-learning module. However, in terms of the significant difference in the level of student's performance before and after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video, the result shows that there is a significant difference in the level of student's performance before and after the use of contextualized artwork instructional video. Lastly, results show that there is a significant difference between the level of student's performance after the use of the self-learning module and contextualized artwork instructional video.

Therefore, the researcher concluded that students struggled in terms of self-learning modules for some reason. First, self-learning modules are purely reading, and most students don't have an interest in reading. Second, the instructions in the module are hard to understand and follow. Third, parents can't guide their children due to a lack of knowledge of academics. Fourth, the sample photo is unclear due to black and white printed modules, so students can't see the proper pattern. Lastly, the self-learning modules stimulate independent learning wherein they will learn everything on their own and students can't justify their learning. Thus, these problems/struggles contribute to a low level of students' performance in Arts.

However, when the intervention was conducted, such as using contextualized artwork instructional videos, the level of performance of the students improved. Through contextualized instructional videos, they understood and followed the instructions, and their creativity increased. Instructional video inspired the students to actively participate in the activity by taking notes, following the instructions, and paying attention to what the teacher did in the video. It only means that the intervention was effective. Thus, the teacher must accompany the modules with instructional videos to support and give clearer instructions on the activity given to the students. Teaching Arts using contextualized artwork instructional videos is an effective strategy for improving students' performance since it does not only test their motor skills but also improves creativity and encourages higher-order thinking skills of the students.

Recommendations

After identifying the teaching strategies that would help students improve their level of performance in the arts according to different criteria and through their own experience, the researcher came up with the following recommendations that would benefit both the

teacher and the students, as well as other people concerned. It is highly recommended that school administrators formulate developmental plans in the Arts curriculum and conduct training or seminars for the teachers to expand their knowledge on various strategies, such as creating instructional videos to support the self-learning modules given to the students. The MAPEH teachers who are aware of the capabilities of the students in their performance tasks must employ varied teaching strategies to aid the struggles of the students in self-learning modules. Thus, MAPEH teachers should accompany the self-learning modules with contextualized instructional videos.

On the other hand, parents, as one of the facilitators of learning in the new normal education, must guide their students in creating their artwork so they may be able to assist and answer the queries of their children in doing such artwork. Likewise, students should be exposed to various techniques of intervention, such as the contextualized artwork instructional video, wherein the goal is to help them improve their performance, so that they may be able to appreciate the applications of concepts and skills in doing their artwork.

In addition, the researcher should develop an intervention program to help the teachers and students in the new normal education, specifically in modular distance learning. Finally, future researchers who may take an interest in research about contextualized artwork instructional videos must take an extra step to dig and enhance this line of study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The data gathered was kept with utmost confidentiality and issuance of informed consent was observed. The participants and their parents willingly agreed to take part and support this study. Whatever the score they got in the study will not affect their grades. The school head was notified regarding the conduct of this study and its possible effect on the class schedule and students' performance.

Acknowledgments

A heartfelt gratitude to our family, especially to our parents for all the love and support throughout our endeavours. To the respondents for taking the time to participate willingly, you are very much appreciated. And to God Almighty, who made all things possible!

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